

Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids Part IX. The Effect of Stirring on the Time Variation of Viscosity of Colloid Arsenic and Antimony Sulphides when Coagulated by Simple Electrolytes in the Slow Region.

By SHRIDHAR SARVOTTAM JOSHI AND T. R. GOPALASWAMI IYENGAR.

The following experiments were carried out in continuation of the work on the kinetics of the coagulation of colloids for some time in progress in these laboratories (Joshi and Viswanath, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 329; Joshi and Menon, *ibid.*, 1933, 10, 600; Joshi and Nanjappa, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 133). It is found that the progress of coagulation in the *slow* region followed by measuring η , the viscosity of the coagulating sol, was marked by (a) discontinuities on η -time curves, and (b) usually though not invariably by a fall in η during the initial stages of coagulation. It is well known that one of the respects in which a colloid differs markedly from a molecular system is the possible influence on the former of such mechanical and allied conditions as the age of the sol, the mode of introducing the coagulating solution, its flow through a capillary, shaking, etc. It was sought in previous work (*loc. cit.*) to keep these factors constant by adhering as far as practicable to a constant experimental procedure. For instance, the last of the factors mentioned above was kept constant by giving twice a rotatory motion to the mixture immediately after mixing. In view of the claims made by some workers (*vide infra*) that stirring has an appreciable influence on the rate of coagulation, it was considered desirable to make systematic experiments to estimate this factor, especially with a view to investigate if the course of a coagulation is appreciably changed by stirring, in respect of the two features observed previously, *viz.*, (a) and (b).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The arsenious sulphide sol used in experiments *a—g'* in Figs. 1, and 2 was prepared by adding intermittently small quantities of a triturated solution of arsenious oxide to a saturated solution of hydrogen sulphide in water. The excess of H_2S was removed by passing a current of hydrogen. The antimony sulphide sol (*cf.* curves *h—m'*, Fig. 3) was prepared as recommended by Joshi and Prabhu (*ibid.*, 1931, 8, 11). It was dialysed for 12 days against repeated changes

FIG 1.

 As_2S_3 Sol.

of hot water and was found free of acid. The concentrations of both sols were determined by coagulating a known volume and weighing the dried coagulum (previously washed free of coagulator). The sol contents were 10.7 and 2.05 g. of As_2S_3 and Sb_2S_3 per litre respectively.

FIG 2.

 As_2S_3 Sol.

The measurements of viscosity were made by Scarpa's method with modifications described previously (Joshi and Viswanath, *loc. cit.*). The temperature of the thermostat was maintained constant at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The suction applied was 26 ± 0.05 cm. in all the experiments. The other precautions and details of experimental procedure have been described in previous papers. The constant k of the instrument was found by observation of the times of rise and fall for water. η is expressed relative to that of water taken equal to unity. In order to study the effect of stirring, η -time observations were made with coagulating mixtures under as far as possible identical conditions with and without stirring. A hand regulated glass stirrer operating vertically and giving 30 strokes per minute was used. The stirring of the mixture was started 1.5 minutes before taking every η -observation, and continued for one minute. These η -time observations taken with and without stirring have been shown graphically by curves $a', b', c', \dots, m'$ and $a, b, c, \dots, m$ respectively in Fig. 1-3. The coagulators used were differently concentrated solutions of KCl,

DISCUSSION.

An examination of the foregoing curves shows that the influence of stirring on the variation of η , the viscosity of a coagulating sol is not appreciable at small concentrations of the coagulator. This is in agreement with the results of Freundlich and Basu (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 115, 203), and of Freundlich and Kroch (*ibid.*, 1926, 124, 155) who have found that vigorous stirring causes coagulation, and moderate stirring has but small effect in the presence of low amounts of the electrolyte. Freundlich and co-workers (*loc. cit.*; *ibid.*, 1928, 139, 368) also find that stirring accelerates coagulation at higher concentrations of the electrolytes provided they are absorbed strongly by the colloid; definite exceptions to this deduction were, however, noted in some cases when stirring appeared to retard coagulation. In the present experiments the mixture was stirred only for a short time before each measurements of viscosity. The last mentioned finding of Freundlich and co-workers applies in part to the present results in the sense that greater the electrolyte concentration, the greater is the divergence between the η -time curves for coagulation with and without stirring (Fig. 1, *cf.* curves dd' ; Fig. 3, hh' , jj'). It is also interesting to point out that with large concentrations of KCl and BaCl₂ the effect of stirring is to cause a general lowering of viscosity. The opposite, however, is the case with KHSO₄ (*cf.* Fig. 3, curves jj' , kk'). Whether this implies a like influence on the rate of coagulation is not certain in view of the results published already (*loc. cit.*) that a viscosity change might not necessarily be a measure of corresponding coagulation produced at any rate in the *slow* region. It was observed previously (*cf.* Joshi and Menon, *loc. cit.*) that the η -variations show pronounced discontinuities when Th (NO₃)₄ is used as a coagulant. This obtains in coagulations now studied with and without stirring (*cf.* Fig. 2).

These results also show that in by far the majority of cases the effect of stirring is sensible only after the initial stages of coagulation. It is also of interest to observe that the occurrence of discontinuities on η -time curves, and of the fall of viscosity during the *initial* stages persist even after the stirring of the mixture, and that the magnitude of the last quantity is approximately constant.

